

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AND THEIR INVOLVEMENT IN EDUCATION

Halimboyeva Feruza Akmalovna

Teacher of the social and humanitarian department of the External Department of Fergana State University

Annotation: children preparing for school education, attention is relatively long - term and conditionally stable . The characteristics of the child's attention are described in role-playing and plot games, in drawing and construction activities, in making toys from clay and plasticine, in perceiving and understanding the speech of others, solving mathematical operations.

Key words: Junior school, subjugation of motives, moral norms, educational activity, educational tasks, educational behavior, self-control, self. assessment, cognitive-affective. When talking about the mental readiness of a six-year-old child, it is often referred to as the mental stage that serves as the basis for a planned, orderly, multifaceted goal-oriented, logically interrelated, coherent elementary education. we mean the level of growth. Also, for education, in addition to the level of mental growth, it is appropriate to take into account such factors as the differences, conditions, uniqueness of the child's life and activities, his health, methodological preparation, acquisition of simple skills. All of the above represent the objective aspects of the child's psychological readiness for school education. There is also a subjective aspect of the child's psychological preparation for school education. His desire to study at school, his aspiration, his desire to communicate with older people are inextricably linked with this preparation. By this time, the child has a correct idea about studying and learning. He understands the responsible duties of the members of the school team and tends to obey them and follow their instructions. But since they are not all the

same, there are important differences between them. Some children want to go to school with their whole body, they continuously count how much time is left for studying, they try to prepare their study materials in advance . Another child goes as far as dropping out of school . A negative attitude towards studying often arises as a result of bullying by adults. Also, the words of brothers and sisters about difficult experiences and situations at school, forcing children to prepare more lessons at home , also created a negative attitude towards studying . Children with a negative attitude towards learning find it difficult to enter the educational environment, they face many mental obstacles. In the organization of school-educational work, the anatomic-physiological characteristics of children of junior school age characteristics , understanding the level of physical disability is the key to success . _ _ _ _ _ weight and lung volume are constantly increasing . Bones of a child (chest, bones , arms) , and spinal cord still contain soft tissue , which means that the bone system is completely intact . o indicates a failed match. Cardiac muscles grow quickly, the diameter of blood vessels becomes slightly larger , the weight of the brain is 1250-1400 grams in the first grade. Analytical-synthetic activity of the cerebral cortex improves , the balance between excitation and inhibition changes , but excitation has a relative advantage . Therefore, it is necessary to take care of the proper growth of the child, to prevent it from being overheated , to strictly follow the regime of studying and learning . , changes the social position, the situation in the class community and family environment, its main task is to study , acquire knowledge , acquire skills and abilities, learn about nature and society. It is about mastering the values . Education requires a certain level of organized , honest striving , willpower, activity , and purposeful activity . Involuntary behavior is replaced by conscious, planned, mental work . The student is always in a certain class group with his peers . Therefore, he always has to protect the interests of the class community , subordinate his personal desires to the general meeting , mutual help , mutual demand , social welfare and sense of duty . there is a task to acquire. In the process of education , the demands placed

on the student become more and more complicated . resistances, internal conflicts arise . At the root of these lies the level of mental deficiency in the child and the contradictions between positive feelings and demands . The increasing demands make the mental growth of the child unstoppable , and as a result of the continuous action of this closed chain , the lack of a person is realized . one of its features is that it has its own needs . In essence , these needs are not aimed at acquiring certain knowledge, skills and abilities, assimilation of the surrounding reality , but only reflect the desire to learn . These needs include the desire to have one's own portfolio, a corner for preparing lessons, a place to put books, the feeling of attending school every day as an adult , etc. In addition, the happy days of the day of knowledge , the moment of admission to the ranks of students, the sincere wishes of the school administration and teachers, and the congratulations of the students of the upper class are positive for the child's feelings. it's a secret. Walking in rows with classmates , playing together, going to the kitchen , and the teacher's instructions are also pleasing to the child . In general, a child of primary school age does not understand the basic meaning and purpose of education , but understands that everyone should go to school . However , he diligently follows the instructions of the adults and engages in his studies. The first grader shows interest in the study itself . In special studies, children were given unnecessary exercises , and they were told in advance that these exercises would not be necessary later, but the children began to perform them willingly . The first good result achieved by the student in personal activity motivates him to achieve other results. The first job in his academic career brings joy and happiness . For example, some students try to read a text several times. Interest in the activity of reading creates interest in its content, creates the need for learning and creates motivation for reading . it is inextricably linked with the feeling of satisfaction from the result . This feeling is enhanced by the teacher's encouragement and forms the student's inclination, desire, enthusiasm to work more effectively . The child 's work is used for the development of skills, knowledge and skills . Their

educational effect will increase only if they are motivated and encouraged . Evaluating the activity of students of junior school age is important in forming a positive attitude towards learning . It is known that oral assessment of children has become a habit in schools , because under the influence of doubt, a first-grader increases his activity , tries to search creatively, even At the beginning, the student does not even notice the difference between good and bad grades , he is more interested in how many grades he got. The teacher's encouragement plays the most important role for him. In the process of education , the teacher uses his authority to be honest , fair , and honest , and inspires students to be diligent and diligent in studying . it is necessary to develop such qualities as concentration , behavior control , self-control, and overcoming difficulties . For this, every aspect should use the method of exposure. A negative feature of the perception of students of junior school age is the weakness in distinguishing objects from each other. They often perceive the studied material not clearly , or even incorrectly , as a result of which exactly similar letters , words, images of objects , shapes, spaces they cannot fully imagine the difference in behavior . For example, they do not distinguish between the letters "q" and "k", the words "reading" and "reading", circles and circles, cross -sections and straight lines . Sometimes they notice things that cannot be covered by the scope of adults' perception. The perceptual activity of primary school students has specific features of perceiving space , time and movement . Due to the lack of life experience, the poor level of knowledge , and the weakness of imagination, these forms of perception are very limited in children . Because they are limited to the simple spatial concepts used in everyday life , they use scientific spatial terms , such as the height of trees, the distance between space and the earth , the volume of seas and lakes, and others . they have difficulty shooting. Because they don't understand big spatial concepts , they ask questions such as : " How many kilometers are the stars apart ? " such questions are born. Children 's perception of time also consists of concepts in a narrow sense , and they do not understand what terms such as century and BC are . The ability

to let go and adapt to the emergency situation will not be good. The main reason for this is the weakness and instability of voluntary attention in them . At the same time, the voluntary conscious attention of children of junior school age is inextricably linked with the motives of reading . Usually , their study motives are divided into long - term and goal - related motives . _ _ _ If you enter, the motives of primary school students are related to reality and reality .

REFERENCES

1. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S., & Boxodirjon o'g'li, V. A. (2022). XORIJ PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 39-47.
2. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *IJTIMOYIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 176-182.
3. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.
4. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILIIY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
5. Ботирова, Н. (2020). Обучающие возможности тестовых технологий. *Профессиональное образование и общество*, (3), 68-71.
6. Ботирова, Н. Д. (2019). Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (61), 4-6.
7. Ботирова, Н. Д. Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников development of productive thinking of younger schoolboys. *Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным наукам. Подробнее на*, 4.
8. Ботирова, Н. Д., & Алимджонова, М. Ю. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОШЛАНГИЧ СИНФ ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИ ЭВРИСТИК ФАОЛИЯТИНИ

РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ТАШКИЛИЙ ОМИЛЛАРИ. Scientific progress, 3(4), 519-524.

9. Botirova Nasiba Djurabayevna INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS . Eastern European Scientific Journal Germany. 128 – 132 p. <http://www.auris-verlag.de>

10. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 914-917.

11. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 1040-1044.

12. Alimjanova, M. (2021). ABOUT GENDER STEREOTYPES. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), 2(06), 72-76.

13. Janabergenova, A. J. (2018). Organization and Forms of Students' Independent Work on Higher Mathematics at Pedagogical University. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (2).

14. Janabergenova, A. J. (2021). Setting Goals on Smart Techniques and Affecting Student Motivation. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 9333-9336.

15. Askarova, D. (2022). FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND BOOKREADERS QUALITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1039-1044.

16. Askarova, D. I. (2022). The Role Of Folk Pedagogy In The Development Of Creativity Of Students Of Higher Educational Institutions. Oriental Journal of Social Sciences, 2(02), 89-96.

17. Dilafruz, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarda Va Oilada Gender Xususiyatlarni Shakllantirish Omillari. Innovation In The Modern Education System, 2(18), 183-189.

18. Askarova, D. I. (2022). USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN

DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(10), 92-97.

19. Askarova, D. I., & Jabborova, M. K. (2022). The Introduction Of Gender Issues In Preschool Education On The Example Of Folk Pedagogy. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(05), 81-87.

20. Jabborova, M. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 129-132.

21. Jabborova, M. (2022). BO'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNI TAYYORLASH TIZIMIDA MALAKAVIY AMALIYOTNING ROLI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 167-173.

22. Kodiraliyevna, J. M. (2022). TARBIYACHI KASBINING MA'NAVIY AXLOQIY NEGIZLARI. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 2), 64-70.

23. Zhabborova, M. R. K. (2021). Мактабгача таълим соҳаси талабаларида бошқарувчанлик қобилиятларини ривожлантириш. *Молодой ученый*, (17), 394-395.

24. Dilafruz, Y., Marifatxon, J., Rasuljonovna, E. Z., & Muqaddasxon, M. (2022). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMGA YANGICHA YONDASHUV. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 3), 121-125.

25. E. Najmiddinov, A. Rasujonov, & J. Rahimov (2022). FARG'ONA VODIYSI SUV HAVZALARIDAGI BALIQLAR GELMINTLARI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 145-151. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335759

26. Najmiddinov, Eldor , Rasuljonov, Adhamjon, & Rahimov, Javohir (2022). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10), 1049-1054.

27. E. Najmiddinov (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА “ИХТИОЛОГИЯ ВА ГИДРОБИОЛОГИЯ” СОҲАЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 152-160. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335800
28. E. Najmiddinov (2022). TABIATNING MAKTABGACHA TA’LIM YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNI BARKAMOL AVLOD BO’LIB SHAKLLANISHIDAGI ANAMIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B8), 149-154. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7336353
29. Юлдашев, Э., & Нажмиддинов, Э. (2013). БРАКОНИДЫ (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) РОДА ROGAS NEES ФАУНЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ. In *Биоразнообразие и рациональное использование природных ресурсов* (pp. 134-136).
30. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., Кучбоев, А. Э., Мухаммадиев, М. А., & Соатов, Б. Б. (2021). Эколого-морфологические характеристики нематод рода *Rhabdochona*-паразитов обыкновенной маринки. *Теория и практика борьбы с паразитарными болезнями*, (22), 387-393.
31. Kuchboev, A. E., Najmidinov, E. K., Mukhamediev, M. A., Karimova, R. R., & Yildiz, K. (2021). Morphological and ecological features of some nematodes of the genus *Rhabdochona* in marinka obtained from Fergana Valley, Uzbekistan. *Journal of Parasitic Diseases*, 45(4), 1084-1089.
32. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 326-329.
33. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). METHODOICAL SUPPORT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 74-76.

34. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 97-102.
35. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 235-239.
36. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 121-123.
37. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289-292.
38. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.
39. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY*

JURNALI, 2(11), 235-239.

40. Asqarov Anvarjon Rahimjon o‘g‘li. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING AQLIY TARAQQIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHIDA O‘YIN RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI FAOLIYAT SIFATIDA. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 207–209.
41. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.
42. To‘lqinovna, Y. D. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MATEMATIK TASAVVURLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 25-31.
43. Yuldasheva Dilshoda To‘Lqinovna (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA BADIY TASVIRLAR ORQALI IZCHIL NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521
44. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 124-130.

45. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 10, 32-35.
46. Ummatqulov, T. (2022). INSON SOG'LOM BO'LISHIDA VALEOLOGIYA FANINING AHAMIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 80-88.
47. SultonaliMannopov, A., AbdusalomSoliev, U., & TokhirShokirov, R. (2021). Development of Uzbek National Singing Art during Independence. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 6845-6853.
48. Шокиров, Т. Н. (2022). МИЛЛИЙ МУСИҚА МАДАНИЯТИ ВА УНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ (фольклор, дostonчилик, мақом мисолида). *Science and innovation*, 1(С3), 31-38.
49. Shakirov, T. N. (2022). SUCCESSION IS THE MAIN PRINCIPLE OF DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL MUSIC CULTURE. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(06), 1-10.
50. Шокиров, Т. Н. (2022). АБУ НАСР ФОРОБИЙНИНГ МУСИҚА ИЛМИГА ҚЎШГАН ҲИССАСИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 353-359.
51. Nurmamatovich, S. T. (2021). Theoretical of national music culture fundamentals.
52. Qizi, G. S., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). The use of anthroponyms and pseudonyms in alisher Navoi's gazelles. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 349-353.
53. Tillaboyeva, G., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). ALISHER NAVOIY ASARLARIDA BADIY TAXALLUSLARNING QO'LLANILISHI. *Студенческий вестник*, (13-5), 70-72.
54. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). ALISHER NAVOIY SHE'RIYATIDA

“SHAXS” TUSHUNCHASI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 182-196.

55. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA LIBOS NOMLARI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 506-514.

56. Mohinur, D., & Rahimjon, U. (2022). A Study Of Memory Processes And Their Development In Preschool. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 62-65.

57. Rahim, U. (2021, May). SOCIAL FACTORS OF THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF MENTAL AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 6-7).

58. Usmonov, R. (2022). O'SMIRLAR XULQIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK G'AYRATLILIK XUSUSIYATLARI TADQIQ ETISH METODOLOGIYASI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 127-135.

59. Usmonov, R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRI SHAXSIGA XOS ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDOSHUVLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 120-126.

60. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.

61. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.

62. Rakhmonovich, U. R. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF

DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 820-824.

63. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.
64. Қурбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
65. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).
66. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). О ‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.
67. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). CHET EL OLIMLARI TOMONIDAN GURUHDAGI O ‘SMIRLAR VA AUTSAYDERLAR MUAMMOSINI O ‘RGANILISHNING OZIGA XOSLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 33-38.
68. Noxida, D., & Saida, Q. (2022). TALABA QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASHNING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 309-314.
69. Dilshodbek O'g'li, R. S. (2022). The Role Of Physical Culture In Providing The Psychological Health Of The Athlete. *Innovative Developments And Research In*

Education, Canada.

70. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH–IJTIMOIY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 66-70.
71. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 215-221.
72. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 256-259.